

A Lagrangian Relaxation Matheuristic for the Selective One-to-One Pickup-and-Delivery Problem

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Abstract. We address the Selective One-to-One Pickup-and-Delivery Problem (SOPDP). The single-vehicle SOPDP, which is NP -hard, requires simultaneously solving two problems: (1) determining how to route an empty delivery vehicle back from its current location to its depot by a scheduled arrival time, and (2) selecting a profit-maximizing subset of spot-market delivery requests along the route subject to the vehicle’s capacity. For finding provably optimal solutions to the multi-vehicle SOPDP, we propose a compact mixed integer programming (MIP) formulation and simple, but effective, preprocessing routines. We also propose a Lagrangian Relaxation Matheuristic (LRM) that takes advantage of multithreading to find high quality solutions within practical time limits. Results from computational experiments on a set of 300 problem instances demonstrate the effectiveness of the LRM. For example, the minimum, median, mean, and maximum running times for Gurobi to solve the MIP for the largest instances are 5 seconds, 56 minutes, 5 hours, and 10 hours respectively. The corresponding times for the LRM are 1, 5, 8, and 30 minutes, respectively; and the minimum, median, and maximum gaps are 0%, 2.98%, and 4.82%, respectively.

Key words: Freight Logistics, Pickup and Delivery, Multicommodity Flows, Integer Programming, Lagrangian Relaxation, Parallel Processing

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1. Introduction

In this paper we consider the selective one-to-one pickup and delivery problem (SOPDP) arising in transportation. The goal of the SOPDP is to maximize total profit by determining routes for a set of delivery vehicles from their current locations to their depot by a scheduled arrival time and selecting spot-market pickup-and-delivery requests along the routes subject to the vehicles’ capacity. Assuming that the vehicles travel at a known average speed, the arrival-time requirement is enforced by limiting the length of the routes. Figure 1 illustrates a feasible solution to a single-vehicle instance of the SOPDP. In the figure, “a vehicle with a 50-ton capacity is currently at node 1 and must return to the depot at location 10 via a path of at most 500 miles. The solution shown in the figure sends the vehicle on the 480-mile path $1 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 10$ indicated by the red arcs. The blue arcs in the figure indicate that the vehicle accepts four requests: (i) location 1 to location 6 (40 tons), (ii) location 1 to location 10 (10 tons), (iii) location 6 to location 10 (30 tons), and (iv) location 8 to location 10 (10 tons). In this solution, the vehicle carries 50 tons traveling from location 1 to location 6, 40 tons from location 6 to location 8, and 50 tons from location 8 to location 10. The numbers next to the dashed arcs indicate the weight of other delivery requests that

are available and close enough to both locations 1 and 10 to be considered, but are not accepted in the solution (Ryan et al. 2025).”

Figure 1 Example Single-Vehicle SOPDP from Ryan et al. (2025)

We say that the problem illustrated in Figure 1 is *selective* because the vehicle is not required to accept any of the requests. Following Hernández-Pérez and Salazar-González (2009), we say the problem is *one-to-one* to emphasize the fact that, unlike vehicle routing problems (e.g., Archetti et al. (2014), and Berbeglia et al. (2007, 2010)), the delivery requests in the SOPDP do not necessarily share a common pickup or dropoff location.

The orienteering problem (Tsiligirides 1984) is a special case of SOPDP (Dong et al. 2022) that has received considerable attention in the literature (e.g., Vansteenwegen et al. (2011) and Gunawan et al. (2016)). Golden et al. (1987) show that the orienteering problem is \mathcal{NP} -hard, which establishes the computational intractability of the SOPDP. Tramp shipping in maritime transportation is another type of SOPDP studied in the literature (e.g., Christiansen et al. 2004 and Brønmo et al. 2007).

Applying the SOPDP to the trucking-based third-party logistics (3PL) industry, Dong et al. (2006), develop heuristics for the single-vehicle SOPDP in which all requests require the full capacity of the vehicle. Yu and Dong (2013) present a mixed-integer program (MIP), an exhaustive search procedure, and a genetic algorithm for the general single-vehicle case. Dong et al. (2022) propose a compact MIP that can be solved significantly faster than the node-arc model proposed by Yu and Dong (2013). Ryan et al. (2025) propose fast heuristics for the general single-vehicle case. Their greedy ensemble (GE) algorithm finds solutions with optimality gaps of 5% or less to 207 of the 280 problem instances in their data set, which includes the problem instances from Dong et al. (2022). In their experiments, the longest running time for GE was 35.1 seconds, and the minimum, mean, and maximum times for CPLEX to solve the compact MIP were 6.17×10^{-17} seconds, two hours, and 57 hours and 42 minutes, respectively.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. We formally define the SOPDP and extend the compact formulation from Dong et al. (2022) to multiple vehicles in Section 2. We present a Lagrangian relaxation of our formulation in Section 3 and describe how it is embedded in our Lagrangian relaxation matheuristic (LRM) in Sections 4 and 5. We summarize results from computational experiments on a set of 300 problem instances that demonstrate the effectiveness of the LRM in Section 6.

2. The SOPDP

In this section we formally define the SOPDP and formulate a mixed integer programming model for solving it.

2.1. Formal Problem Specification

Formally, we specify an SOPDP instance with a network $G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$ in which the nodes in $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ correspond to the starting locations of the vehicles and the locations for optional pickup and/or delivery. Node n corresponds to the depot, which may also be a delivery location. The arcs of the network are denoted by $\mathcal{A} = \{(i, j) | i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{n\}, j \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}\}$, and $\mathcal{R} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ denotes the set of requests. Hereinafter, we assume that the set of requests only includes requests that may be picked up and delivered any time before the vehicles are required to return to the depot.

For arc (i, j) , parameter d_{ij} is the driving distance (in miles) from node i to node j . Note that G is an abstraction of the physical road system; arc (i, j) represents the shortest physical route a vehicle can take from location i to location j . As is common in the logistics literature (e.g., Berbeglia et al. (2007)), we also assume that relevant driving distances satisfy the triangle inequality. For each arc (i, j) that is also in \mathcal{R} , parameter w_{ij} is the weight (in tons) of the request from i to j .

We denote the set of vehicles by \mathcal{V} and the starting location (origin) for vehicle $q \in \mathcal{V}$ by $o_q \in \mathcal{N}$. In this study all vehicles weigh v tons when empty and can carry up to Q tons of cargo. We denote the 3PL's traveling and carrying cost (in dollars per ton per mile) by c . Thus, the costs for a vehicle to traverse arc (i, j) when empty and fully loaded are $c \times v \times d_{ij}$ and $c \times (v + Q) \times d_{ij}$, respectively. We use p to denote the price charged by the 3PL (in dollars per ton per mile). Thus, the revenue received for accepting request $(i, j) \in \mathcal{R}$ is $p \times d_{ij} \times w_{ij}$. The distance limit for the path any vehicle travels from its origin to the depot is denoted by D (miles).

2.2. Mixed Integer Programming Formulation

Our MIP formulation of the SOPDP generalizes the single-vehicle triples formulation proposed by Dong et al. (2022); it uses the binary variable x_{ijq} to indicate whether or not vehicle q traverses arc (i, j) , and binary variable y_{klq} to indicate whether or not vehicle q accepts request (k, l) . Sequence variables $s_{iq} \geq 0$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$, track the relative order in which nodes are visited by vehicle q as in the Miller-Tucker-Zemlin (MTZ) constraints for the TSP (Miller et al. 1960).

The formulation represents the movement of cargo through the network using the triples formulation of multicommodity flow. The triples formulation represents *direct* flow from node i to node j on arc (i, j) implicitly, and its primary decision variables represent flow from i to j that is *diverted* along paths of two or more arcs (Dong et al. 2015). Thus, our formulation uses $\mathcal{T} = \{(i, j, k) \in \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N} : (i, j) \in \mathcal{A} \text{ and } k \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i, j\}\}$ to denote the set of node triples for the network and variable z_{ijq}^k to indicate the amount of flow from node i to node j that vehicle q diverts through node k . Variable θ_{ijq} represents the total flow (i.e., tons of cargo) transported on arc (i, j) by vehicle q .

Using the notation above, our MIP formulation of the SOPDP is given by

$$[\text{P}] \quad \omega = \max_{s,x,y,z,\theta} p \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{(k,l) \in \mathcal{R}} d_{kl} w_{kl} y_{klq} - c \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} d_{ij} \theta_{ijq} - cv \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} d_{ij} x_{ijq} \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{(o_q,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{o_q j q} = 1 \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{(i,n) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{i n q} = 1 \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{(i,k) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{i k q} - \sum_{(k,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{k j q} = 0 \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, k \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{o_q, n\} \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} d_{ij} x_{ijq} \leq D \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V} \quad (5)$$

$$s_{iq} - s_{jq} + (n-1)x_{ijq} + (n-3)x_{jiq} \leq n-2 \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ijq} \leq 1 \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_{ijq} = w_{ij} y_{ijq} + \sum_{(i,k,j) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ikq}^j + \sum_{(k,j,i) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{kjq}^i - \sum_{(i,j,k) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ijq}^k \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, (i,j) \in \mathcal{R} \quad (8)$$

$$\theta_{ijq} = \sum_{(i,k,j) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ikq}^j + \sum_{(k,j,i) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{kjq}^i - \sum_{(i,j,k) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ijq}^k \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{R} \quad (9)$$

$$\theta_{ijq} \leq Q x_{ijq} \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} y_{ijq} \leq 1 \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (11)$$

$$s_{iq} \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, q \in \mathcal{V} \quad (12)$$

$$x_{ijq} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (13)$$

$$y_{ijq} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, (i,j) \in \mathcal{R} \quad (14)$$

$$z_{ijq}^k \geq 0 \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{V}, (i,j,k) \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15)$$

Following the discussion above, the first term in the objective function (1) is the total revenue generated by the accepted requests, and the last term is the total traveling cost for the vehicles. The middle term in (1) is the total of the carrying costs. Constraints (2)–(4) determine the route for vehicle q from its origin to the depot by sending a unit of flow from node o_q to node n . Each vehicle's route is limited to at most D miles by constraint (5). The formulation uses (6) to eliminate subtours from the vehicles' routes. These constraints are adapted from the lifted MTZ constraints proposed by Desrochers and Laporte (1991). Since constraint (6) allows subtours in the linear programming relaxation, we impose node-degree constraint (7) to strengthen the formulation. Constraints (8) and (9) are triples constraints for modeling the movement of cargo carried by

the vehicle as multicommodity flow; see Appendix A for a small numerical example and Dong et al. (2022) for a detailed explanation in the single-vehicle case. Vehicle capacity is enforced by constraint (10), which also ensures the logical connection between the x and y variables. Constraint (11) ensures that no request is accepted by more than one vehicle. Constraints (12)-(15) define the domains for the decision variables.

2.3. Preprocessing

Under certain conditions, the following observations about the triangle inequality allow us to fix some decision variables in [P] to zero prior to solving the model.

Observation 1 *If $d_{o_q i} + d_{ij} + d_{jn} > D$ for vehicle $q \in \mathcal{V}$ and arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$, then vehicle q will exceed the distance limit if it travels to node i , traverses arc (i, j) , and then travels to node n . Thus, x_{ijq} must equal zero in any feasible solution. Furthermore, the triangle inequality implies that the length of any path connecting nodes o_q, i, j and n (in that order) exceeds D . Therefore, if $(i, j) \in \mathcal{R}$, then vehicle q cannot accept the request and y_{ijq} must also equal zero in any feasible solution.*

Observation 2 *If vehicle q 's path from its origin to the depot contains a subpath comprising arc $(i \neq o_q, k)$ and a path from node k to node j , its length must be at least $d_{o_q i} + d_{ik} + d_{kj} + d_{jn}$. Therefore, vehicle q can only divert cargo from node i to node j through node k if $d_{o_q i} + d_{ik} + d_{kj} + d_{jn} \leq D$. This implies that if $d_{o_q i} + d_{ik} + d_{kj} + d_{jn} > D$ for vehicle q and $(i \neq o_q, j, k) \in \mathcal{T}$ then $z_{ijq}^k = 0$.*

In preliminary experiments on problem instances with 20 locations and three vehicles, we found that preprocessing based on these observations reduced the minimum, mean, and maximum solution times from approximately 3, 22, and 104 minutes, to 23 seconds, 1 minute, and 3 minutes, respectively.

3. Lagrangian Relaxation

Relaxing constraint (11), which ensures that no request is accepted by more than one vehicle, decomposes [P] into q single-vehicle instances. This observation motivates the following the Lagrangian dual problem [LD] in which multiplier u_{ij} penalizes violations of constraint (11).

$$[\text{LD}] \quad v_L = \min_{\mathbf{u} \geq \mathbf{0}} \omega(\mathbf{u}) \quad (16)$$

The Lagrangian relaxation $\omega(\mathbf{u})$ for fixed multipliers, $\mathbf{u} = \{u_{ij} | (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}\}$, is shown below as [DS].

$$[\text{DS}] \quad \omega(\mathbf{u}) = \max_{s, x, y, z, \theta} p \sum_{\substack{q \in \mathcal{V} \\ (k, l) \in \mathcal{R}}} d_{kl} w_{kl} y_{klq} - c \sum_{\substack{q \in \mathcal{V} \\ (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}}} d_{ij} \theta_{ijq} \\ - cv \sum_{\substack{q \in \mathcal{V} \\ (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}}} d_{ij} x_{ijq} + \sum_{(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}} u_{ij} (1 - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} y_{ijq}) \quad (17)$$

subject to (2)-(10) and variable domain constraints (12) - (15).

Observe that [DS] can be separated into $|\mathcal{V}|$ single-vehicle problems where $[DS_q]$ is the independent problem for vehicle $q \in \mathcal{V}$. Since it is straightforward, we defer $[DS_q]$ to Appendix B. Relaxation [DS] is motivated by preliminary experiments which indicated that commercial solvers take considerably longer to solve [P] than the single-vehicle MIP. Our SOPDP matheuristic solves the $[DS_q]$ problems in parallel to speed up the subgradient optimization algorithm for solving [DS]. Furthermore, as described in Section 5, the matheuristic uses a straightforward procedure to construct a feasible solution to [P] from solutions to the $[DS_q]$ problems at the end of each iteration of the subgradient optimization algorithm. For convenience, we hereinafter use the term Lagrangian relaxation (LR) to refer to the process of solving [DS] and constructing feasible solutions to [P].

Preprocessing

Observe that in the decomposed Lagrangian dual problem $[DS_q]$, if a variable y_{ijq} 's object-function coefficient, $pd_{ij}w_{ij} - u_{ij}$, is zero or less, then $y_{ijq} = 0$ in the optimal solution. Otherwise, we can increase the objective value by decreasing y_{ijq} to zero without violating any constraints. Therefore, we always fix such y variables to be zero when solving $[DS_q]$.

4. Lagrangian Relaxation Matheuristic (LRM)

In preliminary experiments, we observed that commercial MIP solvers (e.g., Gurobi) tend to find high-quality feasible solutions to [P] relatively early in their exact solution process. But, they also tend to suffer from long run times due to slow improvement in the upper bound (UB) on profit. On the other hand, Lagrangian relaxation converges quickly to a good UB. These observations motivate the design of our Lagrangian relaxation matheuristic (LRM), which uses multi-threading to run an exact algorithm (e.g., Gurobi's branch-and-bound algorithm) and Lagrangian relaxation in parallel. The LRM maintains three sets of bounds that are shared by the two threads: (1) the current (best) lower and upper bounds determined by the exact algorithm, LB_E and UB_E , respectively; (2) the current bounds from the Lagrangian relaxation thread, LB_{LR} and UB_{LR} ; and (3) global bounds $LB = \max(LB_E, LB_{LR})$ and $UB = \min(UB_E, UB_{LR})$. The LRM terminates when $LB = UB$ or a user-selected stopping criterion is met (e.g., the gap between LB and UB is small enough). Algorithm 1 describes the LRM's main routine.

Algorithm 1: Lagrangian Relaxation Matheuristic (LRM)

```

Input : SOPDP instance
Output  $S^*$ , the best solution found
:
1 setUpParameters()
2  $S^* \leftarrow \emptyset$ ; // the solution with highest profit found
3 Initialization:  $u_{ij} \leftarrow 1/|\mathcal{A}|$  (Lagrange multiplier),  $LB \leftarrow -M$ ,  $UB \leftarrow +M$ ,  $LB_{LR} \leftarrow -M$ ,  $UB_{LR} \leftarrow +M$ ,  $LB_E \leftarrow -M$ ,
    $UB_E \leftarrow +M$  ( $M$  is a sufficiently large number)
4 do in parallel
5   Thread 0: LRforSameStartNodes(SOPDP instance,  $S^*$ ) (or LRforDiffStartNodes(SOPDP instance,  $S^*$ ));
6   Thread 1: Solve [P] with an exact method.
7   if a new feasible solution is found, (1) update  $UB_E$ ; (2) if the new profit is better than the current best profit, update  $LB_E$ ;
8   if the optimal solution is found terminate the parallel running;
9 end
10 whichSolverFindsBestBound( $UB, UB_{LR}, UB_E, LB, LB_{LR}, LB_E$ )
11 return  $S^*$ 

```

Line 1 of Algorithm 1 initializes the user-specified parameter values such as the minimum acceptable gap between the global bounds; see Algorithm 3 in Appendix C.1 for details. The notation

S^* in line 3 represents the best solution found by LRM. Line 4 initializes the Lagrange multipliers to the reciprocal of the number of arcs in the network, and the upper and lower bounds described above to sufficiently large and small numbers. Lines 5 through 10 describe the parallel operation. The LRM implements two variants of Lagrangian relaxation for Thread 0: LRforSameStartNodes if all vehicles start at node 1, and LRforDiffStartNodes if the vehicles have unique starting nodes. Each iteration of LR updates LB_{LR} , UB_{LR} , LB and UB if improvements are found. In Thread 1, the SOPDP MIP, [P], is solved by the exact method. Whenever the exact method finds a new incumbent solution, LRM updates LB_E and UB_E accordingly.

Stopping Criteria

As soon as either of the two threads finishes, LRM stops the other and returns the best solution found, S^* . Thread 1 stops when the optimal solution is found or thread 0 stops. Thread 0 stops the LR process if one of the following criteria are met:

1. The accumulated elapsed time for solving [DS] instances meets or exceeds a user-given threshold.
2. The Lagrange multiplier step size is reduced to or below a threshold value set by Algorithm 3.
3. The gap $\frac{UB-LB}{|LB|}$ drops below $LR_gap_tolerance$ set by Algorithm 3. Note that we use the absolute value of LB because the profit could be negative, and for some instances, for example, when there are a relatively few number delivery requests, the optimal solution profit might be negative.
4. The Lagrangian dual problem [LD] has been solved to optimality within a tolerance set by Algorithm 3.

The next section describes the two LR variants.

5. LR Variants

In this section we describe the two variants of LR implemented in our LRM. LR consists of two phases. Phase I solves the decomposed Lagrangian dual problems, [DS_q]. If the combined solution of all vehicles satisfies the relaxed constraint (11), then it is a feasible solution for [P]. If the solution has multiple vehicles accepting the same request (i.e., it violates (11)), Phase II uses the solution from Phase I as a guide to construct a feasible solution for [P] from the solutions to the [DS_q] problems. Section 5.1 below describes Phases I and II for the case where the vehicles have different starting nodes. Note that we focus on the high-level design of the algorithm, which calls several subroutines whose details are given in Appendix C. Section 5.2 is a high-level discussion of how we adapt the LR in Section 5.1 to the case where the vehicles all start from the same node.

5.1. Different Start Nodes

Algorithm 2 describes LR when the vehicles have different starting nodes. Lines 2 to 4 solve the $|\mathcal{V}|$ single-vehicle problems, [DS_q] for each vehicle $q \in \mathcal{V}$, in parallel, and line 5 combines the solutions to generate a solution for model [DS]. Line 6 adds $\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij}$ to the sum of the vehicle profits to calculate the objective function value of [DS], $\omega(u)$. Line 7 sets the LR upper bound, UB_{LR} , to the minimum of its current value and $\omega(u)$. Line 8 checks for improvement in UB_{LR} . If there has been no improvement after a user-specified number of iterations in a row, the parameter LR_λ , which is used to update Lagrange multipliers in Algorithm 4, is reduced by half.

Lines 9 to 19 handle the case that the solution \mathcal{S} satisfies all the constraints of [P]. Line 10 is a stopping criterion; if the term for relaxing (11) into the objective function of [DS] is small enough, \mathcal{S} is an optimal solution for [P] and the LR and LRM procedures can be terminated. If the solution

Algorithm 2: LRforDiffStartNodes

```

Input : SOPDP instance,  $S^*$ 
Output  $S^*$ 
:
1 while  $|\frac{UB-LB}{LB}| > LR\_gap\_tolerance$  do
2   do in parallel
3     solve each  $[DS_q]$  for  $q \in |\mathcal{V}|$  by Gurobi and find solution  $x_q$  and  $y_q$ 
4   end
5    $S = \{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}\}$ ,  $\mathcal{X} \leftarrow \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{|\mathcal{V}|}\}$ ,  $\mathcal{Y} \leftarrow \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{|\mathcal{V}|}\}$ ,  $x_q$  and  $y_q$  are the solution for vehicle  $q \in \mathcal{V}$ 
6    $\omega(u) \leftarrow \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \omega_q(u) + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij}$ 
7    $UB_{LR} \leftarrow \min\{UB_{LR}, \omega(u)\}$ 
8   if  $UB_{LR}$  has no improvement over  $LR\_maxNumNoImprovement$  iterations,  $LR_\lambda \leftarrow 0.5 * LR_\lambda$ 
9   if in solution  $\mathcal{Y}$ , each request  $(i, j) \in \mathcal{R}$  is assigned to no more than one vehicle ( $\sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{Y}_{ijq} \leq 1$ ) then
10     if  $|\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij}(1 - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{Y}_{ijq})| < LR\_complementarity\_tolerance$  then
11        $S$  is the optimal solution,  $S^* \leftarrow S$ , exit while loop
12     else
13        $newProfit \leftarrow \omega(u) - \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij}(1 - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{Y}_{ijq})$ 
14        $LB_{LR} \leftarrow \max\{LB_{LR}, newProfit\}$ 
15       if  $(newProfit > LB)$ ,  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (newProfit, S)$ 
16       if  $(LB_E > LB)$ ,  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (LB_E, S_E)$ 
17       updateMultiplier( $\mathcal{Y}, LR_\lambda, LR_\mu, u, LB, \omega(u)$ )
18       if  $LR_\mu \leq LR_\mu\_tolerance$ , exit while loop
19     end if
20   else
21     // if there are requests assigned to multiple vehicles, fix some y variables and
22     solve [P]
23      $potentialArcSet \leftarrow \text{selectPotentialArcs}(S)$ 
24     presetVar( $S, potentialArcSet$ )
25     Solve the SOPDP instance with fixed variables get the optimum  $obj$  and solution  $S_{LB}$ 
26      $LB_{LR} \leftarrow \max\{LB_{LR}, obj\}$ 
27     if  $(obj > LB)$ ,  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (obj, S_{LB})$ 
28     if  $(LB_E > LB)$ ,  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (LB_E, S_E)$ 
29     updateMultiplier( $\mathcal{Y}, LR_\lambda, LR_\mu, u, LB, \omega(u)$ )
30     if  $LR_\mu \leq LR_\mu\_tolerance$ , exit while loop
31   end if
32    $UB \leftarrow \min\{UB, UB_{LR}, UB_E\}$ 
33 end while
34  $UB \leftarrow \min\{UB, UB_{LR}, UB_E\}$ 
35 terminate parallel running

```

is not optimal for [P], the algorithm executes lines Lines 12 to 19. In this case, we use S as a feasible solution, and $newProfit$ in line 13 is its profit. Line 14, sets the LR lower bound, LB_{LR} , to the maximum of its current value and $newProfit$. Lines 15 and 16 update the global lower bound and corresponding solution by comparing the incumbent solutions from LR and the exact method running in Thread 1. Line 17 uses Algorithm 4 to update the Lagrange multipliers for the next iteration of the while loop. Line 18 checks the step-size stopping criterion. If the step-size for reducing the Lagrange multipliers, LR_μ , is too small, the Lagrange multipliers u will remain the same in the next iteration, which will lead to the same solutions for the $[DS_q]$ problems.

Lines 21 to 30 implement Phase II of the LR, which handles the case that S contains violations of the relaxed constraint (11). In this case, the LRM solves [P] with most of variables for a given vehicle q fixed to values from the solution to $[DS_q]$. For example, if vehicle q is the only vehicle that accepts request (i, j) , then we fix y_{ijq} to 1 and y_{ijk} to zero for every other vehicle $k \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{q\}$. Typically, this reduces [P] to a relatively small MIP that can be solved quickly to resolve the violations of constraint set (11).

Algorithm 5, called in line 22, generates the $potentialArcSet$ based on S . It contains arcs which can be added to a vehicle's route, without violating the distance limit, to replace a request that it and other vehicles accept in their respective $[DS_q]$ solutions. Line 23 calls Algorithm 6 to fix variables

as described above, and Line 24 applies an exact method to solve the resulting instance of [P] to optimality.

The actions in lines 25 through 29 are the same as those in lines 14 to 18 in Phase I. In line 31, which ends each iteration of the while loop, the LRM's upper bound is updated so that it can check the gap at the beginning of the next iteration.

5.2. Same Start Node

Algorithm 7 in Appendix C.5 describes LR when the vehicles all have the same starting node. When all vehicles start from the same node, the Lagrangian dual subproblem $[DS_q]$ is identical for every vehicle. So, Phase I of Algorithm 7 begins by solving $[DS_1]$. Another difference between the LR variants is that Algorithm 7 inspects the top $|\mathcal{V}|$ solutions found for $[DS_1]$, \mathcal{B} . The best solution in \mathcal{B} is assigned to vehicle 1, the next best solution is assigned to vehicle 2, and so forth. If $|\mathcal{B}| < |\mathcal{V}|$, then vehicles $|\mathcal{B}| + 1$ through $|\mathcal{V}|$ are assigned the same solution as vehicle 1. The other difference between the LR variants is that for Algorithm 7 we add the constraints listed Appendix D $[DS_1]$ to preclude the possibility of \mathcal{C} containing multiple solutions with identical x and y values, but different s values.

6. Results

This section summarizes our empirical study comparing an exact method for solving the preprocessed MIP described in Section 2 to the mathheuristic described in Sections 4 and 5. We summarize two computational experiments using SOPDP instances with 10 to 50 nodes, and three vehicles. For each value of $n \in \{10, 20, 30, 40, 50\}$, we tested 10 problem instances. In the first experiment, the vehicles have distinct starting nodes (DSN); in the second, all three vehicles have the same start node (SSN), node 1.

All problem instances in the study have the following parameters: the delivery price and vehicle traveling costs are $p = 1.20$ and $c = 1$ dollars per ton per mile, the weight and capacity of the vehicles are $v = 5$ and $W = 50$ tons, and the maximum allowable travel distance is $D = 1,000$ miles (i.e., the time limit is 20 hours and the vehicle's average speed is 50 miles per hour). The weight of the delivery requests range from 5 to 50 tons in 5-ton increments. These parameter values are taken from the literature (Yu and Dong (2013), Dong et al. (2022), and Ryan et al. (2025)).

The networks in the aforementioned SOPDP literature were generated in a way that ensures that any node j is *reachable* from the vehicle's starting location (i.e., $d_{1j} + d_{jn} \leq D$). However, our analysis of the data determined that multiple-vehicle instances on these networks are prone to simplifying to essentially $|\mathcal{N}|$ different single-vehicle problems since most requests lie in the reachable pickup region of only one vehicle. So, to generate the networks for our instances, we assume that the start nodes are relatively close to each other. For three-vehicle instances, without loss of generality, we assume that vehicles 1, 2 and 3 always start from nodes 1, 2, and 3 respectively, and end at node n . Node 1 and node n 's locations in the Euclidean plane are predetermined as $(250, 500)$ and $(750, 500)$, respectively. Node 2 and 3's locations are randomly generated in a 300-by-300 square with node 1 at the center so that any node j in this square is reachable from node 1. The rest of nodes are placed by randomly generating a location within a 1000-by-1000 square centered at $(500, 500)$ that is retained if it is within reach of the starting location for all three vehicles. The process is repeated until $n - 3$ nodes within the distance limit are found.

Following the design of experiments in Ryan et al. (2025), the problem instances can be divided into three sets: *original data*, *sparse data 1*, and *sparse data 2*. The original data are relatively dense problem instances in which the request set \mathcal{R} typically comprises more than 90% of the arc set \mathcal{A} . To study the effects of request density ($\frac{|\mathcal{R}|}{|\mathcal{A}|}$) on the performance of the proposed solution approaches,

we randomly removed 40% and 80% of the requests from each instance in the original data to create instances for sparse data 1 and sparse data 2, respectively. Note that the request-removal process ensures that each node in $\{4, 5, \dots, n - 1\}$ has at least one in-coming or out-going request.

We implemented the MIP presented in Section 2.2 in AMPL version 20250626 (Fourer et al. 1993). Table 1 gives a representative sample of MIP sizes for after preprocessing by our, AMPL, and Gurobi's preprocessing routines. We solved the (preprocessed) MIPs with Gurobi 12.0.2 (Gurobi Optimization, LLC 2024) running on a network of AMD EPYC 7763 processors (2.45 GHz) each with two CPUs, 128 cores, and 512 GB RAM (SMU Center for Research Computing 2025). Other than giving Gurobi a time limit of 10 hours and 28 threads, we used the default solver settings. Hereinafter, Gurobi runs on problem [P] are referred to as the *exact method* and runs that stopped due to the time limit are said to have *timed out*.

n	Constraints	Continuous Variables	Binary Variables
10	721	873	303
20	2,298	2,391	821
30	5,276	8,581	1,902
40	9,743	24,054	3,497
50	15,732	51,983	5,897

Table 1 Typical (Preprocessed) MIP Sizes

The LRM was implemented in C++20, compiled by gcc 11.2.0, with Gurobi 12.0.1 using OpenMP (OpenMP Architecture Review Board 2008) to make parallel calls to Gurobi to solve the $[DS_q]$ MIPs. We also used Gurobi to solve the [P] MIPs with fixed variables in Phase II of the LR algorithms. As with problem [P], we used Gurobi's default solver setting and 28 threads to solve the $[DS_q]$ instances. We limited LRM's running time to one hour and we set the LR gap tolerance (line 1 in Algorithm 2) to 5%.

6.1. DSN Results

Table 2 summarizes the results for the DSN instances. Note that the gaps are shown as percentages rounded to one decimal place, and solution times are given in hours, minutes, and seconds. With one exception, both methods took less than one minute to run on the 60 DSN instances with 10 or 20 nodes. The exact method found optimal solutions for all 60 problems and LRM found optimal solutions to 53. Overall, the exact method performed well on the 30-node instances. But it required almost three hours to solve one of the instances, which is a significant amount of the vehicles' 20-hour time limit. On the other hand, the LRM was able to find solutions to these instances with gaps of at most 4.63% in less than four minutes of running time each. The exact method found provably optimal solutions for 31 of the 40- and 50-node instances, and timed out on 32. The LRM required an average of 7 minutes and 29 seconds to solve the 40- and 50-node instances, and found solutions with optimality gaps of at most 4.9%. Overall the results show that running time increases with density while the optimality gap decreases. LR found the best solution for 38 instances and the exact algorithm found the best solution for 111 instances. There was one instance for which both algorithms found the best lower bound. LR found the best upper bound for 109 instances and the exact method found the best upper bound for the other 41.

<i>n</i>		Dense				Sparse 1				Sparse 2			
		Exact		LRM		Exact		LRM		Exact		LRM	
		Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time
10	Min	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00
	Med.	0.0	0:00:01	0.0	0:00:01	0.0	0:00:01	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00
	Max	0.0	0:00:10	1.8	0:00:07	0.0	0:00:02	0.0	0:00:01	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:01
20	Min	0.0	0:00:08	0.0	0:00:02	0.0	0:00:02	0.0	0:00:01	0.0	0:00:01	0.0	0:00:01
	Med.	0.0	0:00:31	0.0	0:00:02	0.0	0:00:17	0.0	0:00:03	0.0	0:00:02	0.0	0:00:03
	Max	0.0	0:02:08	4.6	0:00:09	0.0	0:00:38	1.8	0:00:20	0.0	0:00:08	1.4	0:00:20
30	Min	0.0	0:04:34	0.0	0:00:13	0.0	0:01:06	0.0	0:00:05	0.0	0:00:08	0.0	0:00:05
	Med.	0.0	0:11:50	0.9	0:00:25	0.0	0:03:40	0.0	0:00:36	0.0	0:00:40	0.0	0:00:36
	Max	0.0	2:50:22	3.8	0:01:22	0.0	0:13:04	3.0	0:03:44	0.0	0:01:19	0.0	0:03:44
40	Min	0.0	0:51:00	0.0	0:01:05	0.0	0:19:26	0.0	0:01:05	0.0	0:04:12	0.0	0:01:05
	Med.	0.3	10:00:28	2.32	0:02:07	0.0	3:19:54	1.9	0:02:37	0.0	0:19:29	0.0	0:02:37
	Max	1.8	10:00:49	3.6	0:08:26	1.6	10:00:05	4.9	0:12:54	0.0	2:31:17	3.0	0:12:54
50	Min	0.0	10:00:04	0.0	0:01:53	0.0	4:21:50	0.0	0:01:19	0.0	0:05:22	0.0	0:01:19
	Med.	0.7	10:00:21	3.3	0:08:49	1.0	10:00:05	2.6	0:05:23	0.0	0:55:38	0.0	0:05:23
	Max	3.5	10:00:33	4.5	0:29:17	3.1	10:00:12	4.8	0:36:34	3.0	10:00:03	4.9	0:36:34
All	Min	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00	0.0	0:00:00
	Med.	0.0	0:11:50	0.28	0:00:25	0.0	0:03:40	0.0	0:00:36	0.0	0:00:40	0.0	0:00:36
	Max	3.5	10:00:49	4.6	0:29:17	3.1	10:00:12	4.9	0:36:34	3.0	10:00:03	4.9	0:36:34

Table 2 Different Starting Nodes: Comparison of Optimality Gap (%) and Running Times (h:mm:ss)

6.2. SSN Results

Table 3 in Appendix E summarizes the results for the SSN instances; the table shows the same qualitative trends observed in the DSN results. But, the SSN instances were more difficult to solve than the DSN instances. For example, the exact method timed out on one of the dense 30-node instances and the Med. run time increased from just under 12 minutes on the corresponding DSN instances to one hour, and the median run time increased from 3 hours and 19 minutes to 10 hours on the 40-node instances in the Sparse 1 dataset. Likewise, the LRM’s average run time on the 40- and 50-node instances increased from 7 minutes and 29 seconds to approximately 28 minutes. We also note the largest gap for the LRM in this group increased from 4.9% to 7.37%. LR found the best solution for 7 instances and the exact algorithm found the best solution for the other 143 instances. LR found the best upper bound for 91 instances and the exact method found the best upper bound for the other 59.

7. Conclusions

We developed a Lagrangian Relaxation Matheuristic that takes advantage of multithreading to find high quality solutions to the Selective One-to-One Pickup-and-Delivery Problem within practical time limits. Results from computational experiments on a set of 300 problem instances demonstrate the effectiveness of the LRM compared to exact solution by a straightforward application of the Gurobi MIP solver. For example, the minimum, median, mean, and maximum running times for the exact method on the largest instances are 5 seconds, 56 minutes, 5 hours, and 10 hours respectively. The corresponding times for the LRM are 1, 5, 8, and 30 minutes, respectively; and the minimum, median, and maximum gaps are 0%, 2.98%, and 4.82%, respectively.

The LRM runs branch-and-bound and Lagrangian relaxation in parallel threads that share their upper and lower bounds with each other. It can be easily extended to an exact algorithm by relaxing

the time limit and optimality gap stopping criteria. We plan to investigate this approach in future work.

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Appendix A: Triples

In this section we give a triples representation of the solution to the SOPDP instance illustrated in Figure 1 assuming that the figure illustrates the path and selected cargo for vehicle q in a multiple-vehicle instance of the SOPDP. For a detailed derivation of the triples formulation see Dong et al. (2022). The vehicle in the figure takes the path $1 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 10$ and accepts requests (1, 6), (1, 10), (6, 10), and (8, 10); and so the corresponding positive x and y variables are $x_{1,6,q} = x_{6,8,q} = x_{8,10,q} = 1$ and $y_{1,6,q} = y_{1,10,q} = y_{6,10,q} = y_{8,10,q} = 1$.

The flow of cargo is represented by $z_{1,10,q}^6 = 10$, $z_{6,10,q}^8 = 40$, and $z_{ikq}^j = 0$ for all other $(i, j, k) \in \mathcal{T}$. The values of these variables indicate that the 10 tons for request (1, 10) are diverted through node 6, and then diverted through node 8 rather going directly to node 10. The 30 tons for request (6, 10) are also diverted through node 8. Requests (1, 6) and (8, 10) are sent directly along arcs (1, 6) and (8, 10), respectively. The weights of the selected requests are $w_{1,6} = 40$, $w_{1,10} = 10$, $w_{6,10} = 30$, and $w_{8,10} = 10$; and so constraint sets (8) and (9) calculate the arc flows shown in the table below.

Arc	Flow
(1, 6)	$\theta_{1,6,q} = w_{1,6} \times y_{1,6,q} + z_{1,10,q}^6 = 40 + 10 = 50$
(1, 10)	$\theta_{1,10,q} = w_{1,10} \times y_{1,10,q} - z_{1,10,q}^6 = 10 - 10 = 0$
(6, 8)	$\theta_{6,8,q} = z_{6,10,q}^8 = 40$
(6, 10)	$\theta_{6,10,q} = w_{6,10} \times y_{6,10,q} + z_{1,10,q}^6 - z_{6,10,q}^8 = 30 + 10 - 40 = 0$
(8, 10)	$\theta_{8,10,q} = w_{8,10} \times y_{8,10,q} + z_{6,10,q}^8 = 10 + 40 = 50$

Appendix B: [DS_q]

$$[\text{DS}_q] \quad \omega_q(u) = \max_{s,x,y,z,\theta} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} (pd_{ij}w_{ij} - u_{ij})y_{ijq} - c_1 \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} d_{ij}\theta_{ijq} - c_2v \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} d_{ij}x_{ijq} \quad (18)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{(o_q,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{o_qjq} = 1 \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{(i,n) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{inq} = 1 \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{(i,k) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ikq} - \sum_{(k,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{kjq} = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{o_q, n\} \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} d_{ij}x_{ijq} \leq D \quad (22)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ijq} \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (23)$$

$$s_{iq} - s_{jq} + (n-1)x_{ijq} + (n-3)x_{jiq} \leq n-2 \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (24)$$

$$\theta_{ijq} = w_{ij}y_{ijq} + \sum_{(i,k,j) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ikq}^j + \sum_{(k,j,i) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{kjq}^i - \sum_{(i,j,k) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ijq}^k \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{R} \quad (25)$$

$$\theta_{ijq} = \sum_{(i,k,j) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ikq}^j + \sum_{(k,j,i) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{kjq}^i - \sum_{(i,j,k) \in \mathcal{T}} z_{ijq}^k \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{R} \quad (26)$$

$$\theta_{ijq} \leq Qx_{ijq} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (27)$$

$$x_{ijq} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (28)$$

$$y_{ijq} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{R} \quad (29)$$

$$z_{ijq}^k \geq 0 \quad \forall (i,j,k) \in \mathcal{T} \quad (30)$$

$$s_{iq} \in [0, n] \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N} \quad (31)$$

Appendix C: Pseudocode

C.1. setUpParameters

Algorithm 3: setUpParameters

```

1 LR_gap_tolerance ← 0.05
2 LR_complementarity_tolerance ← 0.0001
3 LR_μ_tolerance ← 0.00000001 ; // LR_μ is the step size
4 LR_λ ← 2
5 LR_maxNumNoImprovement ← 3
    
```

C.2. updateMultiplier**Algorithm 4:** updateMultiplier

Input : $y, LR_\lambda, LR_\mu, u, LB, \omega(u)$
Output updated Lagrangian multiplier u

```

1 for  $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$  do
2   |  $slack_{ij} \leftarrow 1 - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} y_{ijq}$ 
3 end for
4  $norm \leftarrow \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} slack_{ij}^2$ 
5  $LR_\mu \leftarrow LR_\lambda * (\omega(u) - LB) / norm$ 
6 for  $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$  do
7   |  $u_{ij} \leftarrow u_{ij} - LR_\mu * slack[i][j]$ 
8   | if  $u_{ij} < 0$  then
9     |  $u_{ij} \leftarrow 0$ 
10  | end if
11 end for

```

Following Fisher (2004), the step size at iteration k is $\mu_k = \lambda_k \frac{\omega(u_k) - \omega^*}{\|Ay_k - 1\|^2}$ where λ_k is a scalar satisfying $0 < \lambda_k \leq 2$, A is the coefficient matrix corresponding to constraint set (11), and ω^* is the lower bound. When μ_k is very small, the solution to [DS_q] will not change since there is very little change to the Lagrange multiplier in the next iteration which is generated by the rule $u^{k+1} = u^k + \mu_k(Ax_k - b)$.

C.3. selectPotentialArcs

Algorithm 5: selectPotentialArcs

```
Input :  $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, p, c, d, w$   
Output potentialArcSet  
:  
1 for  $\forall q \in \mathcal{V}$  do  
2    $availableDistance_q \leftarrow distanceLimit - distance_q$  //  $distance_q$  is the travel distance of vehicle  $q$   
3 end for  
4 for vehicle  $q_1 \in \mathcal{V}$  and  $q_2 \in \mathcal{V}$  do  
5   for request  $(i, j) \in \mathcal{R}$  do  
6     if both  $q_1$  and  $q_2$  pick up the request  $(i, j)$  then  
7       for vehicle  $q \in \{q_1, q_2\}$  do  
8          $availableDistance_q \leftarrow availableDistance_q + dis_{ij}$   
9          $startNodesSet \leftarrow \{i\}$   
10         $endNodesSet \leftarrow \{j\}$   
11        for  $k \in \mathcal{N}$  do  
12          if  $(k, i)$  is on the path of  $q$  but request  $(k, i)$  is not selected then  
13             $startNodesSet \leftarrow startNodesSet \cup \{k\}$   
14             $availableDistance_q \leftarrow availableDistance_q + dis_{ki}$   
15          end if  
16          if  $(j, k)$  is on the path of  $q$  but request  $(j, k)$  is not selected then  
17             $endNodesSet \leftarrow endNodesSet \cup \{k\}$   
18             $availableDistance_q \leftarrow availableDistance_q + dis_{jk}$   
19          end if  
20        end for  
21        for  $k_1 \in startNodesSet, k_2 \in endNodesSet, k_3 \in \mathcal{N}$  do  
22          if  $dis_{k_1, k_3} + dis_{k_3, k_2} \leq availableDistance_q$  then  
23             $potentialArcSet_q \leftarrow potentialArcSet_q \cup \{(k_1, k_3), (k_3, k_2)\}$   
24          end if  
25        end for  
26      end for  
27    end if  
28  end for  
29 end for  
30  $potentialArcSet \leftarrow \emptyset$   
31 for each vehicle  $q \in \mathcal{V}$  do  
32    $potentialArcSet \leftarrow potentialArcSet \cup potentialArcSet_q$   
33 end for
```

C.4. PresetVar

Algorithm 6: presetVar

```

1 // set up some  $x$  to be zero
2 for a vehicle  $q \in \mathcal{V}$  do
3   for a node  $i \in \mathcal{N}$  do
4     if  $i$  is not on  $q$ 's route, neither a node in any arc in  $\text{potentialArcSet}_q$  then
5        $x_{ijq} \leftarrow 0, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}$  and  $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$ 
6     end if
7     if  $i$  is on  $q$ 's path then
8       for node  $j \in \mathcal{N}$  do
9         if  $j$  is also on the path, but  $i$  is visited after  $j$ , then  $x_{ijq} \leftarrow 0$ 
10        if  $j$  is not on the path, nor a node of arcs in  $\text{potentialArcSet}_q$ , then  $x_{ijq} \leftarrow 0$ 
11        end if
12      end for
13    end if
14  end for
15 // set up some  $y$  to be zero
16 for a request  $(i, j) \in \mathcal{R}$  do
17   if request  $(i, j)$  is picked up by multiple vehicles then
18     for  $\forall q \in \mathcal{V}$  do
19       if request  $(i, j)$  is not picked up by  $q$ , and  $(i, j) \notin \text{potentialArcSet}_q$ , then  $y_{ijq} \leftarrow 0$ 
20     end for
21   end if
22   if request  $(i, j)$  is picked up by only one vehicle  $q$  then
23      $y_{ijq} \leftarrow 1$ 
24     for  $q \in \mathcal{V}$  and  $q \neq q$ ,  $y_{ijq} \leftarrow 0$ 
25   end if
26   if request  $(i, j)$  is not picked up by any vehicle, and  $(i, j) \notin \text{potentialArcSet}_q$  then
27      $y_{ijq} \leftarrow 0$  for  $\forall q \in \mathcal{V}$ 
28   end if
29 end for

```

C.5. LRforSameStartNodes

Algorithm 7: LRforSameStartNodes

Input : SOPDP instance, S^*
Output S^*

```

1  $\hat{S}^* \leftarrow \emptyset$  // the best solution found
2 while  $|\frac{UB-LB}{LB}| > LR\_gap\_tolerance$  do
3     solve [DS1], retain the top  $|\mathcal{V}|$  solutions; denote their profits as  $\omega^1, \dots, \omega^{|\mathcal{V}|}$  in  $\omega$  in nonincreasing order, and the corresponding y
       solutions as  $y^1, \dots, y^{|\mathcal{V}|}$ .
4      $\omega(u) \leftarrow |\mathcal{V}| \times \omega^1 + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij}$ 
5      $C \leftarrow$  the set of distinct optimal solutions found.
6     Construct the solution of [DS],  $S = \{X, \mathcal{Y}\}$ .
7     Construct  $S_g = \{X_g, \mathcal{Y}_g\}$  by assigning  $\omega^1$  and  $y^1$  to the 1st vehicle and so on, so that  $\mathcal{Y}_g = \{y^1, \dots, y^{|\mathcal{V}|}\}$ .
8      $UB_{LR} \leftarrow \min\{UB_{LR}, \omega(u)\}$ 
9     if  $UB_{LR}$  has no improvement over  $LR\_maxNumNoImprovement$  iterations,  $LR_\lambda \leftarrow 0.5 * LR_\lambda$ 
10    if in solution  $S_g$ , each request  $(i, j) \in \mathcal{R}$  is assigned to no more than one vehicle ( $\sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{Y}_{ijq} \leq 1$ ) then
11        if  $|C| = |\mathcal{V}|$  then
12            if  $|\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij}(1 - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{Y}_{ijq})| < LR\_complementarity\_tolerance$  then
13                 $LB_{LR} \leftarrow \omega(u) - LR_{item}$ 
14                 $S_g$  is the optimal solution,  $S^* \leftarrow S_g$ , exit while loop
15            else
16                 $newProfit \leftarrow \omega(u) - \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij}(1 - \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{Y}_{ijq})$ 
17            end if
18        else
19             $newProfit \leftarrow \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \omega^q + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} u_{ij} \sum_{q \in \mathcal{V}} \mathcal{Y}_{ijq}$ ,  $\{\omega, \mathcal{Y}\} \in S_g$ 
20        end if
21         $LB_{LR} \leftarrow \max\{LB_{LR}, newProfit\}$ 
22        if ( $newProfit > LB$ ),  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (newProfit, S_g)$ 
23        if ( $LB_E > LB$ ),  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (LB, LB_E, S_E)$ 
24        updateMultiplier( $\mathcal{Y}, LR_\lambda, LR_\mu, u, LB, \omega(u)$ )
25        if  $LR_\mu \leq LR_\mu\_tolerance$ , exit while loop
26    else
27        // if there are requests assigned to multiple vehicles, fix some y variables and
       solve [P]
28         $potentialArcSet \leftarrow \text{selectPotentialArcs}(S_g)$ 
29        presetVar( $S_g, potentialArcSet$ )
30        Solve the SOPDP instance with fixed variables get the optimum  $obj$  and solution  $S_{LB}$ 
31         $LB_{LR} \leftarrow \max\{LB_{LR}, obj\}$ 
32        if ( $obj > LB$ ),  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (obj, S_{LB})$ 
33        if ( $LB_E > LB$ ),  $(LB, S^*) \leftarrow (LB_E, S_E)$ 
34        updateMultiplier( $\mathcal{Y}, LR_\lambda, LR_\mu, u, LB, \omega(u)$ )
35        if  $LR_\mu \leq LR_\mu\_tolerance$ , exit while loop
36    end if
37     $UB \leftarrow \min\{UB, UB_{LR}, UB_E\}$ 
38 end while
39  $UB \leftarrow \min\{UB, UB_{LR}, UB_E\}$ 
40 terminate parallel running
    
```

Notes Since [DS_q] is identical for each vehicle $q \in \mathcal{V}$, it suffices to solve for vehicle 1. The feasible solutions found for [DS₁] are numbered 1, 2, ... in descending order by objective function value (i.e., $\omega_1 \geq \omega_2, \omega_2 \geq \omega_3$, and so on. The number of distinct optimal solutions is $|C|$; and so, $\omega^1 = \omega^2 = \dots = \omega^{|C|} > \omega^{|C|+1}$.

At line 5, the algorithm seeks $|\mathcal{V}|$ solutions of the optimal profit ω_1 . A feasible solution for [DS] can be constructed as $\mathcal{Y} = \{y^1, \dots, y^{|C|}, y^1, \dots, y^1\}$ by assigning y^1 to the last $|\mathcal{V}| - |C|$ vehicles. The solution S_g constructed at line 6 will be identical to the DS solution S if $|C| = |\mathcal{V}|$. Otherwise, it is used as a guide to find a feasible solution (LB) in **presetVar()** in Phase II if \mathcal{Y}_g has at least one request picked up by multiple vehicles.

Appendix D: Constraints for Algorithm 7

For Algorithm 7 we add the following constraints to [DS₁] to preclude the possibility of C containing multiple solutions with identical x and y values, but different s values:

$$s_{o_1 1} = 1 \quad (32)$$

$$s_{n1} \leq \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij} + 1 \quad (33)$$

$$s_{i1} \leq n \sum_{\{j | (i,j) \in \mathcal{A}\}} x_{ij} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{1, n\} \quad (34)$$

Constraints (32) and (33) guarantee that the sequence label the starting node is 1 and the label on the depot node (n) is at most one plus the number of arcs on the route. Constraint set (34) forces the $s_{i1} = 0$ for any node i that is not visited. It follows that $s_{i1} = 2$ if node i is the second node in the route, $s_{i1} = 3$ if node i is the third node in the route, etc. Thus, the addition of (32)-(34) to $[DS_1]$ ensures that there is a unique set of feasible values for the sequence variables corresponding to any given path from the start node to the depot.

Appendix E: SSN Results

n		Dense				Sparse 1				Sparse 2			
		Exact		LRM		Exact		LRM		Exact		LRM	
		Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time	Gap	Time
10	Min	0.00%	0:00:01	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00
	Median	0.00%	0:00:01	0.00%	0:00:01	0.00%	0:00:01	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00
	Max	0.00%	0:00:05	4.39%	0:00:04	0.00%	0:00:02	0.00%	0:00:01	0.00%	0:00:01	0.01%	0:00:00
20	Min	0.00%	0:00:27	0.00%	0:00:02	0.00%	0:00:04	0.00%	0:00:03	0.00%	0:00:01	0.00%	0:00:01
	Median	0.00%	0:01:47	3.48%	0:00:09	0.00%	0:00:24	0.00%	0:00:09	0.00%	0:00:03	0.00%	0:00:02
	Max	0.00%	0:05:00	4.98%	0:00:20	0.00%	0:03:28	2.82%	0:00:30	0.00%	0:00:34	0.00%	0:00:07
30	Min	0.00%	0:05:36	0.00%	0:00:25	0.00%	0:02:03	0.00%	0:00:07	0.00%	0:00:16	0.00%	0:00:09
	Median	0.00%	1:00:30	4.09%	0:00:41	0.00%	0:12:08	0.00%	0:01:24	0.00%	0:01:30	0.00%	0:01:02
	Max	1.65%	10:00:15	4.93%	0:01:36	0.00%	2:14:24	3.06%	0:04:57	0.00%	0:06:23	0.00%	0:04:31
40	Min	0.69%	10:00:04	2.27%	0:03:11	1.15%	10:00:02	1.77%	0:01:34	0.00%	0:28:35	0.00%	0:03:41
	Median	1.89%	10:00:12	3.36%	0:04:50	3.82%	10:00:03	4.50%	0:17:03	0.00%	2:17:19	0.00%	0:39:07
	Max	2.77%	10:05:10	4.82%	0:08:06	4.99%	10:00:07	4.99%	0:55:09	7.37%	10:00:02	7.37%	1:00:00
50	Min	0.01%	5:30:13	0.69%	0:01:15	0.37%	10:00:02	3.45%	0:04:29	0.00%	0:03:10	0.00%	0:01:04
	Median	1.49%	10:00:10	3.34%	0:08:37	3.45%	10:00:02	4.96%	0:33:38	1.11%	7:36:16	2.58%	0:26:37
	Max	4.19%	10:00:31	4.52%	0:29:14	7.61%	10:00:04	7.36%	1:00:00	5.03%	10:00:02	5.77%	1:00:00
All	Min	0.00%	0:00:01	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00	0.00%	0:00:00
	Median	0.00%	1:00:30	3.51%	0:00:41	0.00%	0:12:08	1.19%	0:01:24	0.00%	0:01:30	0.00%	0:01:00
	Max	4.19%	10:05:10	4.98%	0:29:14	7.61%	10:00:07	7.36%	1:00:00	7.37%	10:00:02	7.37%	1:00:00

Table 3 Same Starting Node: Comparison of Optimality Gap and Running Times (h:mm:ss)